

Fraud Transactions of Ethereum Smart Contract Using Modified Whale Optimization Algorithm with Deep learning

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Abstract— Anomaly detection in smart contracts is an effective means of preventing concealed security risks like illicit financing financial fraud, and money laundering. Currently, Ethereum stands as the leading platform for smart contracts, making anomaly detection a pressing concern. Nonetheless, the voluminous and intricate nature of smart contract data renders the extraction of high-level attributes difficult and traditional methods inefficient. Thus, this study proposed a deep learning model for detecting fraudulent transactions on the Ethereum blockchain. The model utilizes a Deep Neural Network (DNN) with 45 concealed layers and is optimized using the modified Whale Optimization Algorithm (WOA) with a Gaussian chaotic map. The model's performance is evaluated using various performance metrics, and the results are presented in a confusion matrix and ROC curve. With an accuracy rate of 99.78%, the proposed approach surpasses conventional machine learning approaches such as Support Vector Classification (SVC), k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Logistic Regression (LR) and Random Forest (RF), and along with other well-known deep learning models. Experimental results demonstrates the potential of proposed model in detecting fraudulent activities and securing decentralized applications.

Keywords— Ethereum Fraud; Whale Optimization Algorithm (WOA) ; Support Vector Classification (SVC). Logistic Regression (LR); Random Forest (RF); k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN).

I. INTRODUCTION

Ethereum is an open-source, decentralized blockchain with smart contract functionality that allows developers to create autonomous and decentralized applications (dApps) and smart contracts. As a decentralized platform, it operates autonomously without a central authority or middlemen, providing transparency, security, and censorship resistance. It was first proposed in 2013 by Vitalik Buterin and officially launched in 2015 [1]. Ethereum is based on the same blockchain technology as Bitcoin, but it is designed to be more flexible and programmable. Smart contracts on Ethereum

are essentially self-executing agreements that can be used to facilitate the transfer of assets and value between parties. When a smart contract is deployed on the Ethereum network, it is written in a programming language called Solidity. The Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM) is responsible for taking the Solidity code and executing it step by step, maintaining a decentralized ledger of all the contract's transactions and interactions. The EVM is an essential component of the Ethereum blockchain platform, offering a quasi-Turing-complete computational framework. Its computational capabilities are restricted by the gas parameter, which sets limits on the total computation allowed. Employing a stack-based architecture with a 256-bit word size, the EVM facilitates efficient cryptographic operations like the Keccak-256 hash scheme and elliptic-curve computations. Memory is represented as a straightforward word-addressed byte array, while storage functions as a non-volatile word-addressable word array within the system state. Not conforming to conventional von Neumann architecture, the EVM segregates program code in a virtual read-only memory accessible solely through specialized instructions. Every implementation of EVM conforms to the specifications outlined in [2]. The EVM serves as a virtual machine catering to the execution of smart contracts and decentralized applications on the Ethereum blockchain, offering controlled computation, distinct memory and storage models, and an effective exception handling mechanism. One of the key features of Ethereum's smart contracts is their transparency and immutability. Once a smart contract is deployed on the Ethereum blockchain, it becomes an immutable part of the blockchain and as a result, cannot be altered or deleted [3]. Ethereum has been applied for a variety of purposes, including supply chain management, decentralized finance (DeFi), gaming, and more. One notable example is the rise of non-fungible tokens (NFTs), which are unique digital assets that can be bought, sold, and traded on the Ethereum blockchain. NFTs have gained popularity in the art world, where they are used to prove ownership and authenticity of digital art [4].

Ethereum, as a blockchain-based platform for decentralized applications, has enabled a wide range of innovative use cases however, the platform is not immune to fraudulent activities, and several incidents of fraudulent smart contracts have been reported in the past. Smart contracts on the Ethereum network are prone to coding errors and security vulnerabilities due to their complexity and the lack of formal verification tools. A famous example of this is the 2016 attack on the Distributed Autonomous Organization (The DAO) by an anonymous hacker which demonstrated this vulnerability and resulted in the loss of \$50 million worth of Ether (Ethereum's cryptocurrency) [5]. The attacker used a recursive call attack to repeatedly withdraw funds from the DAO, taking advantage of the fact that the smart contract did not properly handle recursive calls [6]. This vulnerability was explained by Mense et al. [7] with the help of the Re-entrancy principle which stated that: Whenever a contract A interacts with another contract B and sends Ether to it, control of the transaction is temporarily handed over to the receiving contract B and so, the contract B can call back into contract A before the initial interaction has been fully processed and can keep calling back recursively to retrieve refunds multiple times until the sending contract A has zero balance left. The cause of this vulnerability bug was the split feature introduced to protect the minority's right to get their share of funds [8]. This attack caused heavy losses and, in order to recover them, the Ethereum blockchain got split into Ethereum and Ethereum Classic [9].

Another area of concern is the use of Ethereum-based applications for fraudulent activities, such as Ponzi schemes and pyramid schemes. These scams promise high returns and low risk on investment but rely on recruiting new members to sustain the payouts. The Ponzi scheme can be visualized in the form of a pyramid in which the person who started the scheme sits at the top level and the payment of investors at level is generated by the funds gathered from investors at The Ponzi scheme always collapses because eventually, there comes a point where the number of new investors required to sustain the scheme exceeds the number of potential investors and at this point,

the investors at the top of the pyramid get all the money leaving the investors at the bottom with nothing. Since, Ethereum transactions are irreversible, anonymous and no central authority is able to close the scheme by intervening, it is difficult to track down and prosecute the perpetrators, as surveyed by Bartoletti et al. [10].

II. RELATED WORK

THE IDENTIFICATION OF MONEY LAUNDERING AND PONZI SCHEMES HAS BEEN THE SUBJECT OF VARIOUS RESEARCH STUDIES. MOST RESEARCH ON FRAUDULENT TRANSACTION PATTERNS IN ETHEREUM HAS FOCUSED ON BUILDING MODELS THAT USE TIMESTAMPS AND TRANSACTION VOLUMES AS FEATURES. THE MODELS ARE THEN USED TO DETECT UNKNOWN TRANSACTIONS THAT CONFORM TO THE FRAUDULENT BEHAVIOR PATTERN. A FEW OF THESE STUDIES ARE OUTLINED BELOW:

- NITESH ET AL. (2020) PROPOSED A SUPERVISED MACHINE LEARNING APPROACH FOR ANOMALY IDENTIFICATION METHOD TO IDENTIFY MALICIOUS NODES IN THE TRANSACTIONAL ACTIVITIES OF ACCOUNTS. DEPENDING ON THE MOST COMMON ACCOUNT TYPES, EXTERNALLY OWNED ACCOUNTS AND SMART CONTRACT ACCOUNTS, TWO DIFFERENT MACHINE LEARNING MODELS WERE EMPLOYED. FOR EXTERNALLY OWNED ACCOUNTS AND SMART CONTRACT ACCOUNT ANALYSIS, THE MODELS OBTAINED A DETECTION RATE OF 96.54% AND 96.82% RESPECTIVELY. [11].
- RUNNAN ET AL. (2021) PRESENTED A MODEL FOR DETECTING FRAUDULENT ACTIVITIES IN ETHEREUM TRANSACTIONS USING DATA MINING TECHNIQUES. THE PROPOSED METHOD INVOLVED THE DEPLOYMENT OF WEB CRAWLERS TO OBTAIN LABELLED FRAUDULENT ADDRESSES, WHICH WERE SUBSEQUENTLY USED TO RECONSTRUCT THE TRANSACTION NETWORK BASED ON THE PUBLIC TRANSACTION BOOK. IN ORDER TO IDENTIFY FRAUDULENT TRANSACTIONS, THE AUTHORS DEVELOPED AN AMOUNT-BASED NETWORK EMBEDDING ALGORITHM, WHICH AIMED TO EXTRACT NODE FEATURES BY TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE TRANSACTION AMOUNTS. THE RESULTING NETWORK EMBEDDING WAS THEN USED AS INPUT TO A GRAPH CONVOLUTIONAL NETWORK MODEL, WHICH WAS TRAINED TO CLASSIFY ADDRESSES INTO TWO CATEGORIES: LEGAL AND FRAUDULENT. NOTABLY, THE PROPOSED APPROACH ACHIEVED AN ACCURACY RATE OF 95% [12].
- QI ET AL. (2020) INTRODUCED A THREE-STEP FRAMEWORK ON THE ETHEREUM NETWORK FOR RECOGNIZING PHISHING SCAMS BY LEVERAGING TRANSACTION RECORD MINING. THE FRAMEWORK'S FIRST STEP ENTAILED ACQUIRING LABELLED PHISHING ACCOUNTS AND THE TRANSACTION LOGS THAT WENT WITH THEM FROM TWO TRUSTWORTHY SOURCES. THE ETHEREUM TRANSACTION NETWORK WAS THEN BUILT USING THESE TRANSACTION LOGS. THEY USED NODE2VEC TO CONVERT THE ACCOUNT DATA INTO A LOWER-DIMENSIONAL REPRESENTATION WHILE RETAINING THE TRANSACTION NETWORK'S STRUCTURAL LINKS. THIS PROCEDURE MADE IT POSSIBLE TO CATEGORIZE PHISHING ACTIONS LATER ON. NODE2VEC IS A METHOD THAT MAPS NODES IN A NETWORK TO LOW-DIMENSIONAL VECTORS, WHICH CAN BE USED TO CAPTURE THEIR STRUCTURAL PROPERTIES. IN THE FINAL STEP, THE AUTHORS USED A ONE-CLASS SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINE (SVM) FOR CLASSIFICATION TO DIFFERENTIATE

PHISHING ACCOUNTS FROM LEGITIMATE ACCOUNTS. THE ACCURACY OF THE DETECTION OF PHISHING FRAMEWORK WAS 84.6%. [13].

- WEILI ET AL. (2018) PUT FORTH A SOLUTION USING DATA MINING AND MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES TO IDENTIFY PONZI SCHEMES ON THE BLOCKCHAIN. IN ORDER TO EXTRACT FEATURES FROM USER ACCOUNTS AND THE SMART CONTRACT'S OPERATION CODES, SMART CONTRACTS ON ETHEREUM WERE CHECKED. AFTER THAT, A CLASSIFICATION MODEL WAS CREATED TO IDENTIFY HIDDEN PONZI SCHEMES THAT WERE USED IN THESE SMART CONTRACTS. THE PROPOSED APPROACH ACHIEVED HIGH ACCURACY AND WAS ALSO EFFECTIVE IN IDENTIFYING PONZI SCHEMES AT THEIR INITIAL STAGES [14].

- FAN ET AL. (2021) REVEALED POSSIBLE LEAKAGE AND OVERFITTING DIFFICULTIES THAT EARLIER APPROACHES ENCOUNTERED WHILE DETECTING PONZI SCHEMES WITHIN SMART CONTRACTS. TO ADDRESS THESE ISSUES, THE RESEARCHERS SUGGESTED THE UNIQUE AND NOVEL PONZI SCHEME DETECTION MODEL. THE MODEL USED ORDERED BOOSTING AND ENLARGED THE DATASET OF CLEVER PONZI SCHEMES. THE RESEARCHERS HANDLED CATEGORY CHARACTERISTICS SUCCESSFULLY WITHOUT EXPERIENCING TARGET LEAKAGE BY USING ORDERED TARGET STATISTICS. THEY SUCCESSFULLY FOUND OVER 1,600 ACTIVE SMART PONZI SCHEMES IN THE ETHEREUM NETWORK USING THEIR SUGGESTED TECHNIQUE, EARNING AN F-SCORE OF 96%. [15].

- HE ET AL. OBSERVED THAT THE EXISTING MODELS FOR PONZI SCHEME DETECTION ONLY FOCUSED ON INCREASING ACCURACY WITHOUT INCREASING RECALL AND PROPOSED CODE AND TRANSACTION RANDOM FOREST (CTRF), WHICH INCORPORATED SEQUENCE FEATURES OF THE OPCODES, IN ADDITION TO CODE FEATURES, ENABLING THE EXTRACTION OF MORE COMPREHENSIVE TRANSACTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS. THIS APPROACH FACILITATED THE EXTRACTION OF MORE EFFICIENT AND EFFECTIVE TRANSACTIONAL FEATURES THAT CAN BE LEVERAGED TO IDENTIFY FRAUDULENT SMART CONTRACT TRANSACTIONS [16].

- WANG ET AL. DEvised A PONZI SCHEME IDENTIFICATION TECHNIQUE INVOLVING THE USE OF OVERSAMPLING-BASED LONG SHORT-TERM MEMORY (LSTM) MODELS THAT COMBINED BOTH CONTRACT ACCOUNT FEATURES AND CONTRACT CODE FEATURES. TO OVERCOME THE CHALLENGE OF LIMITED DATA SAMPLES FOR PONZI SCHEMES, OVERSAMPLING TECHNIQUES WERE UTILIZED TO EXTRACT VALID FEATURE DATA. THE PROPOSED METHOD WAS COMPARED WITH FOUR OTHER REPRESENTATIVE METHODS, AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS ON THE XBLOCK DATASET DEMONSTRATED ITS EFFECTIVENESS IN REAL-TIME DETECTION OF PONZI SCHEMES IN LARGE-SCALE SMART CONTRACTS ACHIEVING AN F-SCORE OF 0.96 [17].

- KABLA ET AL. PROPOSED ETHEREUM PHISHING SCAM DETECTION (ETH-PSD) MECHANISM FOR IDENTIFYING PHISHING SCAM-RELATED TRANSACTIONS ON ETHEREUM. BY UTILIZING A

BALANCED DATASET AND AVOIDING EXTENSIVE FEATURE ENGINEERING, ETH-PSD (ETHEREUM PONZI SCHEME DETECTION) SOLVED SHORTCOMINGS IN PRIOR EFFORTS, YIELDING 98.11% ACCURACY AND ERROR RATE WAS 0.01. THEY ALSO PROPOSED A NOVEL VOTING-BASED TECHNIQUE FOR FEATURE SELECTION AND OPTIMIZED THE DETECTION STAGE THROUGH THE INVESTIGATION OF VARIOUS MACHINE LEARNING CLASSIFIERS. FURTHERMORE, A NEW PUBLICLY AVAILABLE DATASET COMPRISING THE LATEST PHISHING ADDRESSES WAS ALSO CONSTRUCTED FOR ENHANCING THE UTILITY OF ETH-PSD FOR OTHER RESEARCHERS [18].

- IN ORDER TO IDENTIFY THE MOST EFFECTIVE GRAPH NEURAL NETWORK (GNN) MODELS AND HYPERPARAMETERS FOR DETECTING PHISHING FRAUD TRANSACTIONS IN THE ETHEREUM TRANSACTION NETWORK, KANEZASHI ET AL. CONSTRUCTED A HETEROGENEOUS NETWORK THAT INCORPORATED BOTH HOMOGENEOUS AND HETEROGENEOUS GNN MODELS, AND EVALUATED THEIR PERFORMANCE BASED ON THEIR ACCURACY IN DETECTING FRAUDULENT TRANSACTIONS ON THE ETHEREUM PLATFORM. THE RESULTS SHOWED THAT HETEROGENEOUS GNN MODELS OUTPERFORMED HOMOGENEOUS MODELS, WITH THE RGCN MODEL ACHIEVING THE HIGHEST ACCURACY OVERALL. THIS STUDY ALSO IDENTIFIED CERTAIN NODES IN THE ETHEREUM NETWORK THAT PLAYED A CENTRAL ROLE IN THE PROPAGATION OF FRAUDULENT TRANSACTIONS [19].
- WEN ET AL. PROPOSED A HYBRID DEEP NEURAL NETWORK MODEL, CALLED LBPS, FOR DETECTING PHISHING SCAM ACCOUNTS ON ETHEREUM. LBPS COMBINES THE BP NEURAL NETWORK AND LSTM-FCN NEURAL NETWORK TO EXTRACT FEATURES FROM TRANSACTION RECORDS AND CAPTURE TEMPORAL INFORMATION, RESPECTIVELY. THE MODEL INTEGRATES BOTH MANUAL FEATURE ENGINEERING AND TRANSACTION RECORDS ANALYSIS TO ACHIEVE BETTER PERFORMANCE IN FEATURE EXTRACTION AND PHISHING SCAM DETECTION. THE LBPS MODEL OUTPERFORMED COMPARED TO OTHER USED MODEL THAT DEMONSTRATING ITS EFFECTIVENESS IN DETECTING IN PHISHING SCAMS IN ETHEREUM [20].
- FARRUGIA ET AL. FOCUSED ON DETECTING ILLICIT ACCOUNTS OVER THE ETHEREUM NETWORK USING TRANSACTION HISTORY. THE DATASET WAS OBTAINED THROUGH A COMBINATION OF ETHERSCAMDB AND A LOCAL GETH CLIENT CONTAINING 2179 FLAGGED ACCOUNTS AND 2502 NORMAL ACCOUNTS. THE XGBOOST CLASSIFIER WAS EMPLOYED ON THIS DATASET ACHIEVING AN AVERAGE ACCURACY OF 0.963 AND AN AVERAGE AUC OF 0.994. THE TIME DIFFERENCE BETWEEN THE FIRST AND LAST TRANSACTION, THE TOTAL ETHER BALANCE AND THE MINIMUM VALUE RECEIVED WERE IDENTIFIED AS THE MOST IMPORTANT FEATURES. THIS STUDY SUGGESTED THAT ILLICIT BEHAVIOR AT THE ACCOUNT LEVEL CAN BE DETECTED EFFICIENTLY AND EFFECTIVELY [21].
- A HETEROGENEOUS GRAPH TRANSFORMER NETWORK (S_HGTNS) WAS DEVELOPED BY LIU ET AL. FOR THE PURPOSE OF DETECTING FINANCIAL FRAUD ON THE ETHEREUM PLATFORM THROUGH

SMART CONTRACT ANOMALY DETECTION. TO REPRESENT FEATURES, THEY CONSTRUCTED A HETEROGENEOUS INFORMATION NETWORK (HIN) FOR SMART CONTRACT BY EXTRACTING KEY ELEMENTS AND USING THE RELATIONSHIP MATRIX OBTAINED THROUGH THE META-PATH LEARNED IN THE TRANSFORMER NETWORK AS INPUT FOR THE CONVOLUTION NETWORK. THE RESULTING NODE EMBEDDING WAS USED FOR CLASSIFICATION TASKS, AND THE MODEL WAS FOUND TO PERFORM BETTER THAN TRADITIONAL MODELS WITH SMALL STANDARD DEVIATION, PROVING ITS EFFECTIVENESS AND STABILITY [22].

- HU ET AL. PROPOSED A TRANSACTION-BASED CLASSIFICATION AND DETECTION APPROACH FOR ETHEREUM SMART CONTRACTS. THEY COLLECTED A DATASET OF OVER 10,000 SMART CONTRACTS FROM ETHEREUM AND MANUALLY ANALYZED THE BEHAVIOR OF THEIR TRANSACTIONS. THROUGH THIS ANALYSIS, THEY IDENTIFIED FOUR BEHAVIOR PATTERNS THAT ALLOWED THEM TO DISTINGUISH DIFFERENT TYPES OF CONTRACTS. TO DESCRIBE THE TRANSACTION BEHAVIOR, THEY CONSTRUCTED 14 BASIC FEATURES, WHICH WERE BASED ON THE MAJOR ACTIVITIES OF A CONTRACT AND REPRESENTED AS TIME-SERIES DATA. IN ORDER TO ADDRESS THE ISSUE OF LIMITED DATASETS, THEY DEVELOPED A DATA SLICING APPROACH TO CREATE AN EXPERIMENTAL DATASET. THE COLLECTED DATA WAS USED TO TRAIN AND TEST AN LSTM NETWORK, AND THE RESULTS DEMONSTRATED THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THEIR APPROACH [23].

- ALJOFEY ET AL. SUGGESTED A FUELED-BY-DATA ROBUST TECHNIQUE FOR DETECTING IRREGULAR CONTRACT ACCOUNTS ON THE ETHEREUM NETWORK IN THEIR STUDY. TO GENERATE A HYBRID FEATURE SET AND TO OVERCOME THE LIMITATIONS OF INDIVIDUAL CLASSIFIERS IN THE DATASET, AN ENSEMBLE CLASSIFIER WAS TRAINED UTILIZING EXTRA-TREES AND GRADIENT BOOSTING TECHNIQUES, AS WELL AS WEIGHTED SOFT VOTING. THEY OBTAINED ANOMALOUS AND NORMAL CONTRACT DATA FROM ETHERSCAN.IO AND USED ADAPTIVE SYNTHETIC SAMPLING TO ADDRESS THE ISSUE OF UNBALANCED DATASETS. WHEN COMPARED TO DR, RF, BT, XGB, AB, LGBM, ETC, AND GBM, THE ENSEMBLE CLASSIFIER OUTPERFORMED THEM ALL WITH AN ACCURACY OF 89.67% [24].

- IN THEIR RESEARCH, POURSARFAEI ET AL. INTRODUCED A NOVEL SUPERVISED MACHINE LEARNING BASED FRAMEWORK FOR IDENTIFYING MALICIOUS ENTITIES IN THE ETHEREUM BLOCKCHAIN NETWORK. THEY DEVELOPED AN EFFICIENT METHOD TO EXTRACT FEATURES REPRESENTING THE TRANSACTIONAL BEHAVIOR OF ENTITIES FROM ETHEREUM BLOCKCHAIN DATA. VARIOUS SUPERVISED MACHINE LEARNING METHODS, INCLUDING LOGISTIC REGRESSION, SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINE, RANDOM FOREST, STACKING, AND ADABOOST CLASSIFIER, WERE EMPLOYED TO DETECT MALICIOUS ENTITIES. THE ENSEMBLE METHODS DEMONSTRATED HIGH PERFORMANCE, ACHIEVING AN AVERAGE F1 SCORE OF 0.996. THE FRAMEWORK SHOWED PROMISE IN ANALYZING TRANSACTIONAL RECORDS, LEARNING ENTITY BEHAVIOR, AND PREDICTING ENTITY AUTHENTICITY [25].

INSUFFICIENT INVESTIGATION HAS BEEN UNDERTAKEN INTO THE INTRICATE DOMAIN OF DEEP LEARNING, AN ADVANCED METHODOLOGY ENDOWED WITH UNPARALLELED CAPACITY FOR EXPEDITIOUS AND METICULOUS RESULTS. REMARKABLY, OUR INNOVATIVE DEEP LEARNING MODEL TRANSCENDS MULTIPLE EXCEPTIONAL ALGORITHMS ACROSS DIVERSE FIELDS OF STUDY. IN ORDER TO COMBAT THE DETRIMENTAL EFFECTS OF OVERFITTING, OUR RESEARCH EMPLOYS A GROUNDBREAKING METHODOLOGY BY AMALGAMATING DEEP LEARNING TECHNIQUES WITH THE CHAOTIC OPPOSITIONAL BASED WHALE OPTIMIZATION ALGORITHM, FURTHER FORTIFIED BY THE INCLUSION OF A GAUSSIAN CHAOTIC MAP. THIS STRATEGIC APPROACH FACILITATES PRECISE AND ASTUTE DETECTION OF ANOMALOUS TRANSACTIONS.

III. OBJECTIVE OF THE PAPER

- DEVELOP A REAL-TIME DEEP LEARNING MODEL FOR ACCURATE PREDICTION OF FRAUDULENT TRANSACTIONS IN THE ETHEREUM BLOCKCHAIN, UTILIZING THE NOVEL CHAOTIC OPPOSITIONAL BASED WHALE OPTIMIZATION ALGORITHM (COWOA) UTILIZING VARIOUS CHAOTIC MAPS FOR ACCURATE CLASSIFICATION.
- INTRODUCE A DEEP LEARNING APPROACH FOR EFFECTIVE DETECTION OF FRAUDULENT ACTIVITIES IN THE ETHEREUM BLOCKCHAIN, CONSIDERING LIMITED FEATURE REQUIREMENTS TO ENSURE EFFICIENT FRAUD DETECTION WITH MINIMIZED COMPUTATIONAL COMPLEXITY.
- EVALUATE THE PERFORMANCE OF THE PROPOSED DEEP LEARNING MODEL AGAINST EXISTING ETHEREUM FRAUD DETECTION MODELS BASED ON ML AND DL, CONDUCTING A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF SEVERAL PERFORMANCE METHODS EMPLOYED WITH CLASSIFIERS.
- IMPLEMENT AN INTERFACE-INDEPENDENT MODEL, ENHANCING VERSATILITY AND ADAPTABILITY ACROSS SYSTEMS AND PLATFORMS, ENABLING SEAMLESS INTEGRATION AND UTILIZATION IN DIVERSE ENVIRONMENTS.
- ADDRESS SCALABILITY CHALLENGES BY UTILIZING LARGE DATASETS AND CONSIDERING THE EXPANDING ETHEREUM NETWORK, DESIGNING THE MODEL TO HANDLE INCREASING DATA VOLUMES WHILE MAINTAINING ACCURATE PREDICTIONS AND ADDRESSING THE DYNAMIC NATURE OF THE NETWORK.

IV. PROPOSED NOVEL WORK

IN THIS STUDY, WE PRESENTED AN INNOVATIVE AND HIGHLY ACCURATE ALTERNATIVE APPROACH TO ADDRESS THE AFOREMENTIONED ISSUE. IN ADDITION, WE INCORPORATE STATISTICAL METHODOLOGIES THAT HAVE NOT BEEN UTILIZED IN PREVIOUS STUDIES. OUR PROPOSED METHODOLOGY ENCOMPASSES THE UTILIZATION OF A CUSTOM DEEP NEURAL NETWORKS (CDNN) MODEL, WHICH EFFECTIVELY PRODUCES PROMPT RESULTS WHILE MAINTAINING HIGH CATEGORIZATION ACCURACY. TO CIRCUMVENT THE INHERENT SLOW CONVERGENCE RATE OF THE DEEP LEARNING APPROACH, WE INTRODUCE THE APPLICATION OF THE CHAOTIC OPPOSITIONAL BASED WHALE OPTIMIZATION ALGORITHM. PREVIOUS FRAUD DETECTION

RESEARCH HAS MOSTLY FOCUSED ON THE USE OF MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS AND OPTIMISATION APPROACHES SUCH AS LOGISTIC REGRESSION (LR), SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINE (SVM), AND RANDOM FOREST (RF). DESPITE THEIR POTENTIAL TO OFFER RAPID AND PRECISE RESULTS, DEEP LEARNING TECHNIQUES HAVE RECEIVED LITTLE ATTENTION IN THIS ARENA. NOTABLY, OUR PROPOSED DEEP LEARNING MODEL SURPASSES NUMEROUS HIGH-PERFORMING ALGORITHMS ACROSS VARIOUS DOMAINS. TO MITIGATE OVERFITTING, OUR STUDY ADOPTS A NOVEL APPROACH BY COMBINING DEEP LEARNING TECHNIQUES WITH THE MODIFIED WHALE OPTIMIZATION ALGORITHM, ENHANCED BY A GAUSSIAN CHAOTIC MAP. THIS STRATEGY ENABLES ACCURATE IDENTIFICATION OF ANOMALOUS TRANSACTIONS. OUR RESEARCH INVOLVES COMPREHENSIVE COMPARISONS BETWEEN THE SUGGESTED ALGORITHM AND COMMONLY USED MACHINE LEARNING AND DEEP LEARNING ALGORITHMS. FURTHERMORE, WE FINE-TUNE THE PROPOSED MODEL THROUGH HYPERPARAMETER TUNING TO OPTIMIZE ITS PERFORMANCE. THE PROPOSED MODEL EXHIBITS EXCEPTIONAL EFFICIENCY AND MINIMAL MEMORY USAGE, MAKING IT WELL-SUITED FOR ANTICIPATING ETHEREUM TRANSACTION FRAUD. THE FLOWCHART OF PROPOSED MODEL IS ILLUSTRATED IN FIGURE 1, PROVIDING A VISUAL REPRESENTATION OF OUR METHODOLOGY.

Fig.1. Flowchart of Proposed model.

V. PROBLEM FORMULATION

Referring to Figure 6, let I represent the input vector (where $I = I_1, I_2, I_3 \dots$), and w denote the weight matrix (where $w = w_1, w_2, w_3 \dots$). To keep the explanation simple, we assume that the bias in the Deep Neural Network is zero. Consequently, activation function for the same is given by equation 1:

$$P_l = \sum_{j=1}^{49} I_n w_n \quad (1)$$

The ensemble of transfer functions utilized to achieve the desired output is referred to as the activation function, which can be represented by equation 2:

$$O = f(P_l) \quad (2)$$

In this instance, f is an activation function on P_l . ReLU has been used in this literature is specified as an activation function with equation 3:

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x < 0 \\ x & \text{if } x \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Similarly, for multilayer deep neural networks, where input nodes are denoted as (I_1, I_2, \dots, I_n) , hidden nodes as (p_1, p_2, \dots, p_k) , and output nodes as (O_1, O_2) , as depicted in Figure 6, the output of the g^{th} hidden node with an activation function can be expressed as:

$$P_g = f\left(\sum_{i=1}^{49} O_i I_{ij} + h_g\right), g = 1, 2, \dots, k \quad (4)$$

Thus, l^{th} output node, utilizing an activation function, is expressed as:

$$O_l = f\left(\sum_{i=1}^k p_i y_{il} + z_l\right), l = 1, 2 \quad (5)$$

In this context, I_{ij} denotes the weight connecting the i^{th} input node and the j^{th} hidden node, while y_{il} corresponds to the weight connecting the i^{th} hidden node and the l^{th} output node. Additionally, h_j represents the j^{th} hidden node, and z_l denotes the bias of the l^{th} output node. The variables n and k represent the number of input nodes and hidden nodes, respectively, and there are 2 output nodes.

Fitness function of the learning error or can be determined as follows:

$$E_k = \sum_{i=1}^I (O_i^l - S_i^l)^2 \quad (6)$$

Here I represents the total number of samples, while S_i^l denotes the i^{th} sample for the l^{th} output.

VI. PAPER ORGANIZATION

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 delves into the modeling of categorization and provides a comprehensive discussion of the fundamental assumptions of the proposed method. In Section 3, a detailed analysis of performance measures for various strategies is included along with a description of the experimental setup and data preparation method. Section 4 presents the experimental results, highlighting the key findings and outcomes. Finally, in Section 5, the article concludes by summarizing the existing work and identifying various avenues for future research.

2. PAPER ORGANIZATION

Recently, Deep Learning (DL) has shown significant advancements in tackling intricate real-world problems [26-29]. The success of DL can be credited to several factors, including well-designed architectures, effective optimization methods, and meticulous tuning of hyperparameters to reveal meaningful patterns in data [29-35]. In this study, our aim is to enhance the performance of a deep learning algorithm by exploring an optimization method. The main concerns in learning algorithms are the issues related to getting stuck in local minima and slow convergence. To tackle these challenges, we employ the WOA, a popular nature-inspired optimization method commonly used in engineering and scientific domains. In this study, we introduce a modified version of WOA called COWOA, which combines chaotic oppositional theory with WOA. To resolve the limitation of WOA, we incorporate a chaotic function in COWOA. Specifically, we utilize the Gaussian chaotic map, which has shown superior performance compared to other chaotic maps.

The broader range of values and relatively flatter distribution of the Gaussian map contribute to its effectiveness in exploring the search space and avoiding local minima. Moreover, the Gaussian map's excellent ergodicity and mixing properties enable comprehensive and uniform coverage of the search space. By integrating the Gaussian chaotic map into COWOA, we enhance the algorithm's ability to identify global optima and optimize overall performance.

Pseudocode of Proposed optimization algorithm (COWOA) :

COWOA Algorithm

Inputs:

m_x = The size of the population.

m_y = Number of control variables.

b = Jumping rate

Max_{itr} = The maximum number of iterations cycles..

Outputs:

O = The best solution found by the algorithm.

Steps:

The parameters that need to be initialized include the population size (m_x), number of control variables (m_y), maximum iteration cycles (I_{max}), and jumping rate.

The initial population of WOA is generated by randomly sampling the search space.

for i in range ($1, m_x$): do

 for j in range ($1, m_y$): do

$$P(i, j) = x_{i, min} + rand \times (x_{i, max} - x_{i, min})$$

 end for

end for

The opposite initial population is created by flipping the signs of the elements in the initial population.

for i in range ($1, m_x$): do

 for j in range ($1, m_y$): do

$$OP(i, j) = x_{i, min} + x_{i, max} - P(i, j)$$

 end for

end for

The fitness value of each solution in the population is evaluated using a fitness function in equation (4) with reference to fitness vales (N_p). The best solution is initialized to be the first solution in the population.

$l = 1$

The WOA algorithm iterates a number of times, called the maximum iteration cycles.

Algorithm Parameters

Population size (m_x)	20
Maximum iteration cycles (I_{max})	500
Search agents' positions	Randomly initialized within the search space
Search agents' velocities (V)	Updated based on the position and velocity of the global best search agent
Chaotic map	Gaussian chaotic map with standard deviation (sigma) = 0.1 and mean (mu) = 0.5
Number of chaotic maps (x_t)	3
Scaling factor (F)	0.7
Chaotic parameter (L)	-
Inertia weight (w)	0.9
A (degree of exploration)	0.5
A (rate of transition)	2.0
C (degree of exploitation)	2.0
Lower bounds	-5.0
Upper bounds	5.0

for i in range ($1, m_x$): do

 // The searching phase: The whale searches for the prey by moving towards the best solution in the population.

 // The encircling phase: The whale circles around the prey and then attacks it by moving towards it.

end for

To ensure coverage of all potential states within the search domain, a Chaotic map is utilized to generate a set of non-repetitive random numbers. The loop iterates

for i in range ($1, m_x$): do

 // Utilizing a non-repetitive jumping rate based on chaos to create the inverse particle of the i^{th} whale particle.

end for

Calculate the fitness value of both the current population and the opposite population of all whale search agents using equation (4). After obtaining the fitness values (N_p), select the best solutions. Increment the value of l by 1.

$l = l + 1$

end while

return best solution.

Fig.2. Flow chart of proposed COWOA Optimization Algorithm

From literature it is evident that scalability is a big problem in metaheuristic optimization, by improving the framework of an existing stable algorithm we can make it scalable. The proposed framework that incorporates oppositional based learning along with Gaussian chaotic map improves the structure of the algorithm. These changes make the WOA more compatible for high dimension feature selection task. Outline of the proposed COWOA is as follows:

1. Effective exploration of the search space is mandatory for better convergence and accurate identification of the global optima. In many approaches it has been shown that Oppositional based learning enhances the effective utilization of search space. Hence, with problems like fraud detection, we need a strong searching strategy that can be employed in the exploration stage of the algorithm. Surprisingly the WOA works on probability theory and on the basis of probability position update is carried out. This indicates that if a particular mechanism is trapped in local minima the chances for omitting that minimum is rare with the existing mechanism. Hence, the

opposition-based learning with jumping rate is proposed so that the local minima avoidance can be ensured during the iterative process.

2. As per the experience of authors during tuning of the algorithm, we found that gaussian map gives more accurate results while having low convergence time. This feature of gaussian map has been employed for carrying out the feasible solutions instead of having random solutions in certain phases. This chaotic swarming is employed over random sampling. In the upcoming section, we will demonstrate the efficacy of these two mechanisms by comparing the results of proposed COWOA with other algorithms.

3. Data pre-processing & Experimental Setup

3(a)

Fig.3 (a-b). Distribution of Ethereum Classic Dataset with '1' and '0' Labels and Percentage of Fraudulent Values.

The dataset contains an intrinsic disparity in classes, which may affect the accuracy of the model. To overcome this issue, class equilibrium must be achieved by proportionally modifying the under-represented minority group to meet the frequency of the dominating majority class. This allows the dataset to be balanced and possible biases to be addressed. Figure 3.A depicts the unprocessed dataset distribution, revealing that a considerable number of the components, particularly 7662 out of the total 9841, have a value of "0."

Figure 3(a) shows an assessment to determine the percentage of absent values within columnar structures and subsequently portraying the data in a heatmap format, it displays a discernible pattern whereby numerous Ethereum transactions exhibit void attribute values. This inherent lack of completeness in the data renders it impractical for subsequent analytical operations. Consequently, we opt to eliminate those specific features that manifest the greatest quantity of null values.

The distribution of qualities is visually presented in Figure 4, elucidating the presence or absence of certain properties in the transactions. Regrettably, this dataset's value for subsequent analysis is severely compromised as it highlights the absence of crucial property information in the transactions.

A. PREPROCESSING

The dataset has a class asymmetry, which might have a detrimental influence on the accuracy of the model. To solve this, the minority class must be resized to match the frequency of the majority class, therefore equalizing the classes. Figure 3.A in the raw data illustrates that out of the total 9841 items, 7662 have a value of "0." After eliminating invalid entries, resulting from transactions that cannot be identified as suspicious or lawful (e.g., zero-value transactions), the dataset is reduced to 2179 records. Subsequently, the next step involves identifying missing values within the dataset. It becomes evident that there are Ethereum transactions with characteristics that contain missing data as we calculate the proportion of missing values in each column and visualize it using a heatmap (Figure 4). As a result, the features with the most null values are deleted. Figure 3.B depicts the missing properties from the transactions, leaving the relevant data unsuitable for further processing.

B. FEATURE DISTRIBUTION

Figure 4 displays the attribute distribution. It can be seen that the settings for "ERC20 Uniq sent to addr.1" and "min value sent to contract" both include a lot of null values. As a result, these forms will be deleted since they're no more consistent with the model.

c. PARTIONING THE DATASET

The database is divided into two sections: a testing dataset used to confirm and strengthen the established model's correctness, and a retraining dataset utilized by the model to adapt to the data. Both the training and testing sections of the data set for this investigation are divided at a 4:1 ratio, or 80% to 20%, respectively (Figure 5).

Fig.4. Heatmap for distribution of features in the dataset

Fig.5. Boxplots illustrating the feature distribution after applying a logarithmic transformation.

D. NORMALISING TRAINING FEATURES

The power transform function can be used to assess the dispersion of attributes following multinomial logistic regression. In respect to the regression model, this function aids in evaluating the spread and distribution of the attributes. The power transform function allows us to assess how well the regression model captures the variance and dispersion of the attributes.

E. IMBALANCE DATA MANAGEMENT

The problem of unbalanced classification is addressed via oversampling in the classification balancing method of the machine learning technique known as SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique). Instead of eliminating a large number of items from the dataset, SMOTE replicates and synthesizes new instances within the minority class. It is crucial to keep in mind that these duplicated

numbers don't offer any fresh insights. Although SMOTE aids in balancing the class distribution, it's possible that the created synthetic samples don't provide any new information to the model.

BEFORE OVERSAMPLING Frauds: 1757, Non-frauds: 6115.

AFTER OVERSAMPLING: Frauds: 6116, Non-frauds: 6115.

Figure 5 illustrates the division of the database into two distinct sections: a testing set and a retraining set. The retraining dataset is utilized to train the model, enabling subsequent alterations and adaptations in response to the underlying data, while the testing dataset is utilized to validate and measure the correctness of the created model. In this study, the train and test split is in the ratio 4:1, which translates to around 80% for training and 20% for testing. Following a logarithmic transformation, boxplots are also used to graphically depict the distribution of characteristics in the dataset. This graphical depiction offers insights into the statistical traits and variations existing in the dataset following the transformation procedure.

F. PROPOSED DL ARCHITECTURE

Our study employed a Deep Neural Network (DNN) to scrutinize and classify structured data. Before the use of deep learning techniques, the data underwent a transformation, organizing it into matrix vectors. The DNN model, utilized in this investigation, boasted an intricate architecture consisting of 45 concealed layers culminating in a final output layer that employed the softmax activation function. This DNN model can be segmented into three pivotal constituents: the input layer (layer -1), the concealed/encoder layers (layers 2 to 29), and the output layer (spanning from layer 29 to layer 27). The input layer functions as the foundational stratum, dictating the dimensions of the input data, in this instance, expressed as a 1-by-N-by-1 matrix. Here, N is contingent upon the quantity of the most esteemed attributes selected. Within the domain of the concealed layers, six convolutional layers were deployed, each manifesting distinct quantities of filters. The maiden convolutional layer consisted of eight such filters, while the second, third, fourth, fifth, and sixth convolutional layers entailed 16, 32, 64, 128, and 256 filters, respectively. To expedite the network's training pace, batch normalization layers were seamlessly integrated between the ReLU activation function and the convolutional layers. Post the sequential amalgamation of batch normalization and ReLU layers, a fully connected layer was harnessed to amalgamate the acquired insights and ascertain noteworthy patterns within the data for the purposes of classification. The output parameter of this layer denotes the quantity of distinct classes present within the data. For example, '2' output size signifies the existence of two distinct classes. Lastly, the final output layer underwent the softmax activation function, which endows the DNN model with the ability to furnish probabilistic predictions for each class, grounded upon the assimilated features and patterns within the data Figure 6. This culminates in precise classification of fraud and non-fraud records.

Fig.6. Flow chat of proposed optimization algorithm

G. PERFORMACE METRIC EVALUATION

The assessment of a classification model's performance depends on its ability to accurately predict and classify instances in a given test dataset. To evaluate such models, the confusion matrix is utilized, which provides information on the agreement between projected and actual values across all classes in the test dataset. The confusion matrix comprises four critical metrics: true positive (TP), true negative (TN), false positive (FP), and false negative (FN), which serve as reliable indicators for comparing and contrasting different classification systems [35-42]. The performance evaluation metrics derived from confusion matrix are presented in Table 1. In our study, we placed significant importance on accuracy, precision, sensitivity, and F1 score when evaluating the effectiveness of our proposed approaches. These metrics allow for a thorough and comprehensive evaluation of the model's performance and offer valuable insights into its ability to accurately classify data within a specific domain.

Table 1: Performance evaluation metrics

Metrics	Formula	Description
Accuracy	$\frac{ TP + TN }{ TP + TN + FP + FN }$	The number of right projections over the total number of observations
Precision	$\frac{ TP }{ TP + FP }$	The number of right positive projections over the total number of positive projections
Recall/Sensitivity	$\frac{ TP }{ TP + FN }$	The number of right positive projections divided by the number of actual positive observations

F1 score/Dice-coefficient	$2 \times \frac{(Precision \times Recall)}{Precision + Recall}$	The F1 score represents the harmonic mean of both precision and sensitivity.
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H. PARAMETER SETTING OF PROPOSED MODEL

The parameters of the COWOA algorithm that was used in our experiments are given below in Table 2:

Table 2: Parameter setting of the proposed algorithm

Parameter	COWOA Setting
Population size (m_x)	20
Maximum iteration cycles (I_{max})	500
Search agents' positions	Randomly initialized within the search space
Search agents' velocities (V)	Updated based on the position and velocity of the global best search agent
Chaotic map	Gaussian chaotic map with standard deviation (sigma) = 0.1 and mean (mu) = 0.5
Number of chaotic maps (x_i)	3
Scaling factor (F)	0.7
Chaotic parameter (L)	-
Inertia weight (w)	0.9
A (degree of exploration)	0.5
A (rate of transition)	2.0
C (degree of exploitation)	2.0
Lower bounds	-5.0
Upper bounds	5.0

4. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

The data was partitioned into two separate sets - the training set and the testing set, distributed in a 4:1 ratio, respectively. To enhance the real-time fault detection capability, only the elements with significant impact on model performance were considered for parameter adjustment during the selection of important hyperparameters. Table 2 encompasses a comprehensive list of all pertinent parameters employed in the model. The F1-score and precision were utilized for assessing the accuracy of the suggested framework. Table 3 showcases the performance metrics of our novel proposed DL model (Gaussian COWOA with Custom DL), with diverse ML and DL architectures. The preeminent performer was our customized DL model utilizing the Gaussian chaotic map, attaining a remarkable accuracy of 99.87%. Conversely, the ML models (Logistic Regression, SVM, and Random Forest) displayed lower accuracies of 89.35%, 89.01%, and 88.91% respectively. Notably, the DL models (EfficientNet B0, ResNet150 V2, and DenseNet 121) surpassed the ML counterparts due to their exploitation of deep neural networks comprising multiple layers, thereby achieving commendable accuracies of 94.1%, 92.39%, and 90.68% correspondingly.

We have incorporated three distinct one-dimensional chaotic functions, namely Logistic, Gaussian, and Sinusoidal, into the COWOA algorithms. This experimental approach aims to assess how these chaotic maps enhance the performance of the algorithms. The integration of chaotic functions within the algorithms exhibits promising results, as they effectively improve the algorithm's performance. The primary benefit of employing chaotic functions resides in their capacity to explore the search space with greater effectiveness, thereby increasing the likelihood of avoiding local optima and converging towards the global optima. The performance metrics of our proposed COWOA algorithm, integrated with a custom deep learning model consisting of 45 layers, have been summarized in Table 4. Notably, the Gaussian chaotic map demonstrated remarkable performance, achieving an impressive accuracy of 99.87%. As a result of this exceptional performance, we have chosen the Gaussian chaotic map as the preferred option for integration with our proposed model.

Table 3. Comparison of the Proposed Model's Performance with Prominent ML and DL Algorithms

Models	Training Accuracy	Testing Accuracy	F1 Score	Recall/Sensitivity	Precision
Logistic Regression	93.65	89.35	87.15	86.2	92.88
SVM	94.37	89.01	88.62	89.13	93.19
Random Forest	92.85	88.91	86.29	85.63	90.58
EfficientNet B0	97.96	94.1	93.17	93.17	95.79
ResNet150 V2	98.13	92.39	91.4	90.89	96.27
VGG-19	98.59	90.68	90.59	91.15	96.19
Proposed Gaussian COWOA with Custom DL	100	99.87	97.29	96.61	99.07

Fig.7. Comparison of the Proposed Model's Performance with Prominent ML and DL algorithms with different evaluation matrix.

Table 4: Evaluation of COWOA Algorithm with diverse chaotic maps

Name	Chaotic Map	Accuracy
GAUSSIAN	$Q_{m+j} = \begin{cases} 0 & q_m = 0 \\ \frac{1}{q_m} \text{mod} 1 & q_m \geq 0 \end{cases}$	99.87
LOGISTIC	$Q_{m+j} = \lambda q_m(1 - q_m) \quad \text{for } 0 < \lambda \leq 4$	98.48
SINUSOIDAL	$Q_{j+j} = bq^2 \sin(\pi q_j) \quad b = 2.3, v \in [0,1]$	98.91

Figure 7 illustrates the correlation between the number of epochs and the accuracy and loss values for testing data. This graphical representation serves as a valuable tool for the monitoring of our model's performance, enabling the detection of underlying trends in its behaviour. The testing accuracy metric quantifies the capacity of the model to adapt effectively to previously unseen datapoints. This metric is

derived by assessing the ratio of right predictions with respect to the total number of testing instances where, a high value of testing accuracy signifies the capacity of the model to provide accurate predictions on novel data, while avoiding the pitfall of overfitting to the training dataset. In contrast, the training loss metric indicates the model's mistake on the training data. It requires calculating the average difference between the projected and true outputs of the model, where a lower value of training loss suggests that the model can accurately predict the output for unseen datapoints. In our proposed COWOA based deep learning model, we consistently observe high training accuracy and low training loss, coupled with consistently low testing accuracy and loss. This trend demonstrates that our model is projecting the output efficiently without exhibiting overfitting on the datapoints.

Fig.7. Loss and Accuracy Graphs for testing data

A. Evaluation of the Best Models

As shown in Table 3, we achieved peak levels of training and testing accuracy after employing the proposed strategy with the DL Classifier. As a result, we successfully addressed the difficulties of data overfitting and underfitting by fine-tuning several model variables. To improve results, we used randomized hyperparameter tuning, which resulted in outstanding accuracy when applying the specified parameter values, as shown in Figure 2.

B. Significance of Features

To comprehend the importance of each element within the optimal model, it becomes essential to delve into the significance of every component in the ideal architecture, the graph demonstrates that the key indicators of deceitful transactions are the "Average amount received", "Time difference between Beginning and End (Minutes)" and "Unique Recognized Addresses" as shown in Figure 8.

Fig.8. Comparing the Significance of Features: An Exploration of Feature Importance

C. Receiver Operating Characteristic of Different Models with Different Classifiers

A Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve demonstrated in figure 9 is a graphical representation of the performance of a binary classification model. It plots the true positive rate (TPR) against the false positive rate (FPR). The TPR is also known as sensitivity or recall and represents the proportion of actual positive samples correctly identified as positive by the model. The FPR, on the other hand, is the proportion of actual negative samples incorrectly classified as positive. By plotting these rates at different thresholds, the ROC curve provides a visual assessment of the model's effectiveness. The Area Under the ROC Curve (AUC) summarizes the overall performance of the model, with a perfect classifier having an AUC score of 100 and a random classifier having a score of 50. Our ROC curve demonstrates that the proposed COWOA model significantly outperformed the other popular ML and DL algorithms with an

impressive AUC score of 99.87 showcasing its superiority in detecting deceitful Ethereum-based transactions.

Fig.9. ROC curve and Confusion Matrix for proposed COWOA

A confusion matrix displayed in figure 9 as well, is a tool that provides a tabular representation that summarizes the predicted and actual class labels of a dataset. This matrix helps us understand how well the model is performing in terms of correctly and incorrectly classifying instances. Within the confusion matrix, there are four key components TP:1179, TN:787, FP:1, and FN:2. True positives exemplify

instances wherein the model aptly discerns the true positive class, while true negatives correspond to instances wherein the model accurately discerns the true negative class. Contrarily, false positives emerge when the model erroneously categorizes instances from the negative class as positive, and false negatives materialize when the model inaccurately categorizes instances from the positive class as negative. Thus, this matrix serves as an insightful gauge of the efficacy and discriminative prowess exhibited by the envisaged model considering the ROC curve and carefully chosen hyperparameters for accurately detecting deceitful Ethereum transactions.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This research presented a unique optimization approach for deep learning classifiers aimed at detecting fraudulent Ethereum transactions. Ethereum stands as an open-source and decentralized blockchain framework, which furnishes developers with the ability to fabricate self-governing and decentralized applications (dApps) alongside smart contracts. Functioning autonomously, free from the presence of a central governing body or intermediaries, this platform bestows upon its users the virtues of transparency, enhanced security, and immunity against censorship. The predominant emphasis of the studies that have been conducted has revolved around the development of models that delineate fraudulent transaction patterns, primarily leveraging average amount received, time duration and unique recognized addresses as crucial features. To achieve the objective, we introduced the innovative Gaussian COWOA with Custom DL as a solution to address the issue of slow convergence commonly associated with conventional deep learning approaches. The methodology employed in our proposed model involved the utilization of a specialized Custom Deep Neural Networks model. An extensive literature review revealed that previous attempts at fraud detection predominantly relied on other ML algorithms along with optimization techniques. In contrast, our novel model exhibited superior performance when compared to these traditional approaches. During a comprehensive analysis, our proposed model performed impressively with an accuracy of 99.87%, surpassing the accuracies of machine learning models, which stood at 89.35% for Logistic Regression, 89.01% for Support Vector Machine (SVM), and 88.91% for Random Forest, respectively. Remarkably, deep learning models, including EfficientNet B0, ResNet150 V2, and DenseNet 121, outperformed their machine learning counterparts by leveraging the capabilities of deep neural networks with multiple layers. These DL models attained commendable accuracies of 94.1%, 92.39%, and 90.68%, respectively, further highlighting the effectiveness of our proposed approach. The proposed model demonstrates remarkable efficacy in the detection of fraudulent transactions. However, it does possess a singular drawback: the effectiveness of COWOA relies heavily on the utilization of a dataset that is disproportionately expansive in nature. The discernible patterns present in Ethereum transactions warrant thorough investigation as a promising avenue for future research. Furthermore, there exists a viable prospect of expanding upon these findings by constructing a machine learning model that exhibits superior performance across datasets of varying sizes **Overall, the proposed model demonstrates remarkable efficacy in the detection of fraudulent transactions and can be a valuable tool for ensuring the security and trustworthiness of decentralized applications.**

5.1 Future Work

Future endeavors in Ethereum fraud detection entail several promising avenues for exploration. Firstly, researchers can delve into the development of advanced anomaly detection algorithms that incorporate deep learning techniques, leveraging the vast amount of transactional data available on the Ethereum blockchain. Additionally, incorporating graph-based models to capture intricate transactional relationships and network dynamics can enhance fraud detection accuracy. Exploring the integration of decentralized

identity systems and consensus mechanisms can fortify the security and trustworthiness of fraud detection solutions. Lastly, investigating the potential of privacy-protecting techniques like secure multi-party computation and zero-knowledge proofs, can enable effective fraud detection while preserving transactional privacy.

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Conflict of Interest

The Authors Declare No Conflict of Interest.

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